

Speech Development Of Children With Deficiencies In Intellectual Development With The Help Of Staged Games

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Abstract: This article describes the problem of speech development of children with intellectual disabilities with the help of a dramatized game. Also, the contents of correcting incorrect pronunciation in speech, forming correct pronunciation skills, teaching children to listen carefully to speech, phonemic perception, sound analysis and composition skills are described.

Keywords — game, dramatized, speech, didactic, story-driven, eventful, vocabulary, specialized.

INTRODUCTION.

Currently, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, all conditions have been created to create a comfortable and safe environment for children who are lagging behind in their development in the system of new generation preschool education organizations and multidisciplinary specialized preschool education organizations.

Among children with special needs who are educated in such specialized organizations, there are relatively more children with mental retardation.

For many years, game activity has served as a subject of study for scientific research. This activity has been used continuously in the educational process. The role of the game in the educational process of children with various disabilities is incomparable. The game is not just a pleasure for the child, but the first tool that teaches social skills, a developmental activity and a process that teaches communication. During the games, we can also learn some abilities and characteristics of the child. The main purpose of especially didactic games is aimed at increasing the development of mental activity.

Didactic games become his main work tool if the teacher can use this activity properly and effectively in the case of properly organizing education. A teacher can directly influence the child's personal characteristics, feelings, thinking, will, and behavior during the control and management of game activities. This proves how important the role of games is in a child's life and in the natural process of education. This field is used as the main method of teaching a child, which requires that the game activity be performed in accordance with pedagogical requirements.

Modern education is characterized by the two-way orientation of the methods of pedagogical influence, which takes into account the aspirations of not only pedagogues, but also students. The main difficulty in this matter is that there are no clear means of achieving results in the child's mental development. The fact is that it forces us to constantly change and update our tools to achieve results in the mental and spiritual development of mentally retarded children during the use of didactic games.

Scientists such as A.P.Usova, Z.M.Boguslavskaya, have comprehensively studied the issues of using didactic games in the educational process with children with intellectual disabilities.

A.L. Wenger, N.V. Nischeva, V.N. Avanesova, A. 9 A. Kataeva, E.A. Strebeleva, A.I. Sorokina, N.G. Morozova, P.I. Pidkosisty, N.D. Sokolova, L.S. The researches of Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev, D.B. Elkonin and many other scientists show that the practical importance of learning games is recognized by mankind.

Is related to the centuries-old experience of using didactic games

Simulated games are also a form of teaching children. Its origins in folk pedagogy created educational games based on the combination of games with songs and actions. In the staged game, all structural elements characteristic of children's activity in the game: goal, summary, game activity, rule, result are summarized.

In staging games, children get involved in the game process, they clearly demonstrate positive qualities such as heroism, bravery, kindness, enthusiasm, which are directly related to the inner life of the heroes of the story and fairy tales. In this process, children's speech activity, vocabulary, and worldview expand.

The selection of works of art and fairy tales for staging requires adults to take into account the young characteristics, interests, and desires of children.

The following requirements are set for the selection of literary works:

1. Ideological and spiritual perfection of its content.
2. Artistically meaningful.
3. The number of participants and roles in the play (the more, the more important the play).
4. Along with the good content, it also has many types of actions.
5. Be suitable for expressive reading.
6. The content should be interesting and connected with life

Children like to act out folk tales. For example, "Turnip", "Zumrad va Kimmat", "Boğirsok" and others. Children feel the

need to stage other folk tales in different ways (through puppet, shadow, shadow theater).

In order for them to remember the work of art, it is used to reproduce it, show it on stage, show pictures, and didactic games.

Make pretend play fun and last a long time

the necessary equipment must be prepared and properly guided. Adults

performing the role of a game director, taking into account children's behavior, abilities, and aspirations. children who actively participated in the game are specially encouraged, and they determine which works should be staged in the future

Acting games are a type of independent creative play for children, in which works of art and stories are performed by children in roles. These games form children's positive moral qualities, such as will, discipline, and the ability to control their own behavior and consider the actions of others.

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The organization of staged games includes the following stages:

I stage. Choosing a work of art for staging. When choosing a work of art, the following requirements should be observed: 1) the number of participants in a fairy tale or story should be large; 2) it is necessary to pay attention to the diversity of not only the content of the work, but also the actions in it; 3) the work should be suitable for expressive reading; 4) the content of the work should be interesting and emotional; 5) the work should be suitable for children's age.

II stage. Reading the content of a fairy tale or story selected for staging.

III stage. Making children remember the work: re-reading, individual work on what each child says, showing pictures.

IV stage. In order for the game to be interesting and last for a long time, it is necessary to prepare the necessary materials and clothes for the game and to properly implement the leadership.

Children's thinking expands and their interests develop through action-packed games. Through role-playing games, children get to know the daily life of the people around them, their relationships, and ways of getting married. Children always imitate adults, a little girl caressing her doll repeats her mother's words, cradles her doll and sings, this is the only game in which family skills are formed. we can observe. In addition, through games such as "Doctor", "Barbershop", "Shop",

"builders", "tailors", "Kindergarten", "School - school", interest in the profession, activity, Feelings such as respect for the work of others, amicableness, kindness, and kindness are cultivated.

Despite the diversity of the plot of the games, they belong to special groups

it is possible to attach. For example, the great psychologist EA Arkin recommends the following classification of games:

1) to production (technique); games related to industry, agriculture, construction, professions;

2) games related to household and social life, livelihood, preschool education organization, school, everyday life;

3) military: war-war games;

4) dramatized: games related to movies, plays, etc

Game activity affects the work and development of absolutely all psychological activities. Thus, random actions, random interests and improved memory are observed during games. In the game environment, preschool children learn better and receive more information according to the direct instructions of the leader.

Educational activity is also formed in the game activity. It doesn't come directly from the game. Education is focused on adults. In this way, preschool children begin to learn while playing. Adhering to these principles, they enter into normal learning activities.Z

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